

DASSI DATA ACQUISITION POLICY

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DASSI - Data Archive for Social Sciences in Italy

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Data Archive for Social Sciences in Italy (DASSI) is a research infrastructure which provides support to the scientific community by preserving and sharing data produced in the social sciences field. The document sets out the principles and criteria used in the process of selecting and evaluating data which will be acquired from the archive.

Collection purposes

DASSI preserves research data which makes it possible to achieve at least one of the following objectives:

- strengthening *secondary analysis* in scientific research
- supporting *teaching and learning*
- facilitating the *replicability and validation* of research
- supporting the development of surveys and studies, policies and interventions at local and national level in various socio-economic sectors, through access to data, tools, resources and advanced services for Open Science and Open Innovation

For the data to be acquirable, it is necessary for it to enable the development of new studies and/or the incorporation of existing data; or be a potential support for teaching, learning, the development of research and innovation capabilities; or enable replication of the research, control of the data used and the validation of sources, analyses and the results obtained.

Scope of collection

DASSI focusses on social sciences at large, promoting the deposit of research data produced by all researchers belonging to this scientific domain.

The archive acquires research data relating to Italian society (i.e. data regarding Italy or data from other countries besides Italy for comparative purposes) or collected by Italian researchers.

Selection and appraisal criteria

DASSI archives relevant data for social sciences in accordance with the above purposes. Data selection and appraisal are based on the following criteria:

Documentation

DASSI preserves well documented data, so the selection is focused on the possibility of having satisfactory knowledge of the process of constructing the data relating to the whole *life cycle*. The documentation and all the accompanying material must address:

- *Context/study*: information needed to describe the context or study within which data were created. All the information is included relating to the objectives of the research, the methodology adopted, techniques and instruments for data collection, the sampling plan, etc.
- *Structure*: information relating to the contents of the data. All the information is included on the construction of the variables, the labels, the coding system, any scripts to transform the data, transcription procedures, etc.

Detailed documentation describing the collection, organisation, processing and contextual relevance of the data is therefore essential.

Data access

In order to be able to manage the data accurately and process it easily, DASSI should receive data that meets the following requirements:

- *Integrity*: data must not be corrupted or damaged, infected by a virus, illegible or incomplete;
- *Format*: DASSI manages the data by transforming it into the most suitable formats to guarantee its long-term preservation. In order to be able to satisfy this need, the following formats are accepted:

Data type	Accepted format
Numeric	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ SPSS (*.sav, *.por) ■ STATA (*.dta) ■ SAS (*.sas7bdat) ■ R (*.RData) ■ MS Excel (*.xls, *.xlsx) ■ MS Access (*.mdb, *.accdb) ■ Comma-separated values (*.csv) ■ Tab-separated values (*.tab, *.tsv)

Data type	Accepted format
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ OpenDocument (*.ods, *.odb) ■ Fixed-width format (*.dat)
Textual	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ PDF/A (*.pdf) ■ PDF (*.pdf) ■ MS Word (*.doc, *.docx) ■ RichText (*.rtf) ■ Plain Text format (*.txt) ■ OpenDocument (*.odt) ■ Data Interchange Format (*.htm, *.xml, *.json, etc.)
Geographic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ ASCII (*.asc, *.txt) ■ ESRI Geodatabase (*.gdb) ■ ESRI GRID (*.adf, *.grd) ■ ESRI Shapefiles (*.shp) ■ Geographic Markup Language (*.gml) ■ GeoJSON (*.json) ■ JPEG 2000 (*.jp2) ■ KML (*.kml, *.kmz) ■ MIF/MID (*.mif, *.mid) ■ OGC GeoPackage (*.gpkg) ■ TIFF e GeoTIFF (*.tif, *.tiff) ■ ArcGIS Pro (*.aprx) ■ QGIS (*.qgs, *.qgz)
Digital audio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Free Lossless Audio Codec (FLAC)(*.flac) ■ WAV file (*.wav) ■ MPEG-1 Audio Layer 3 (*.mp3) ■ Ogg Vorbis (*.ogg, *.oga) ■ Audio Interchange File Format (AIFF) (*.aif)
Digital video	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ MPEG4 (*.mpg4) ■ Moving Picture Experts Group MPEG-2 (*.mpg2)

Data type	Accepted format
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ QuickTime (*.mov) ■ Lossless AVI (*.avi) ■ AVCHD video (*.avchd) ■ Ogg Vorbis (*.ogg, *.oga)
Digital image	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ TIFF (*.tif, *.tiff) ■ JPEG (*.jpeg, *.jpg) ■ Raw image format (*.RAW) ■ PNG (*.png) ■ GIF (*.gif) ■ BMP (*.bmp)

Compliance with ethical and legal principles

DASSI only preserves data that complies with the laws on copyright and personal data protection, and which is created in accordance with the ethical principles of scientific research. In relation to these aspects, only data is accepted which enables a clear and unique identification of the holders of property rights and copyright.

In addition, DASSI only accepts *anonymised data*, i.e. in a form which can reasonably prevent identification of the people involved, unless the consent of the participants has been collected. Consequently, the data cannot contain any direct identifier (such as name, address, vehicle licence number, tax code, etc.), or any indirect identifier (such as place of work, salary or other information which, combined with other publicly available data sources, could enable the identification of the individuals involved). During the appraisal, then, a careful analysis is undertaken of the disclosure risk and, should this risk be found, measures will be agreed with the data owner necessary to anonymise the data correctly.

Finally, the informed consent provided by the subjects involved in the research should not prevent the information being conserved, shared and reused beyond the original purposes for which it was collected.

If the deposited data meets the scope and purposes outlined above but fails to meet these criteria, DASSI will notify the depositor of the necessary steps to preserve the data, and offer tailored assistance. DASSI reserves the right to refuse the data in the following

cases: the data would be more suitable for another body or institution (for example, a more suitable subject-specific archive); no agreement has been reached on the conditions to access and disseminate the data; the materials deposited do not have sufficient documentation; the data is not in digital format or is in an obsolete format that is difficult to convert or make usable.

Monitoring and review

The policy is reviewed and updated every three years. DASSI regularly monitors the changes in its designated community, the ethical and legal aspects, and the technological and methodological innovations, in order to guarantee an adequate and relevant policy.

The original of this document was drawn up in the Italian language. The Italian version is the authentic version and shall prevail over the English version in all matters of interpretation and construction.